

Synthesis of Mannich Bases from Coumarin Derivatives and Screening for their Biological Activity

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THE Mannich bases of 7-hydroxy and 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins synthesised with aliphatic amines have been found to have powerful stimulating effect on central nervous system¹. It was therefore thought of interest to synthesise Mannich bases incorporating various DL-amino acids² like glycine, alanine, valine, serine and methionine as a basic component with a view to observe if such compounds could be of biological significance.

- I R=H, R'=CH₃
 II R=CH₃, R'=CH₃
 III R=CH₃, CH₂, S. CH₃, R'=CH₃
 IV R=-CH(CH₃)₂, R'=CH₃
 V R=CH₂OH, R'=CH₃
 VI R=H, R'=H

The structures of the Mannich bases I-VI prepared were assigned on the basis of analogy with the known substitution reactions on 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and from their satisfactory elemental analysis, infrared and proton magnetic resonance spectra. All compounds were screened for their effects on central nervous system of mice. They showed no activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

Mannich bases were synthesised by the following method. Coumarin derivative (0.01 mole), DL-amino acid (0.01 mole) and formalin 40% (0.01 mole) in 80% ethanol were heated under reflux for 3 to 4 hr. The product separated on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from 80% ethanol, yields are usually about 75-80%. VI was obtained in 65% yield.

N-(7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-coumarinyl)glycine (I): M.p. 245-46° d.; ν_{\max} (nujol): 3400 (broad), 1720, 1600 cm^{-1} ; pmr (δ , CF₃COOH): 2.65 (3H, s, -CH₃), 4.4 (2H, broad, -NHCH₂COOH), 4.96

(2H, broad, CH₂NH), 6.53 (1H, s, H-3), 7.25 (1H, d, J=9Hz, H-6), 7.95 (1H, d, J=9Hz, H-5). (Found: C, 59.06; H, 5.072; N, 5.45. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₃O₅N; C, 59.31; H, 4.94; N, 5.32%).

N-(7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-coumarinyl) α -alanine (II): M.p. 265-66° d; ν_{\max} (nujol): 3400 (broad) 3150 (broad), 1730, 1590 cm^{-1} ; pmr (δ , CF₃-COOH): 1.97 (3H, d, J=7Hz, -NHCH(CH₃)-COOH), 2.65 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 4.52 [1H, q, J=7Hz, -NHCH(CH₃)COOH], 4.95 (2H, broad, -CH₂NH), 6.55 (1H, s, H-3), 7.25 (1H, d, J=9Hz, H-6) 7.94 (1H, d, J=9Hz, H-5). (Found: C, 60.53; H, 5.594; N, 5.166. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₅O₅N; C, 60.64; H, 5.41; N, 5.05%),

N-(7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-coumarinyl)methionine (III): M.p. 246-48° d; ν_{\max} (nujol): 3400 (broad), 3150 (broad), 1730, 1620 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 56.57; H, 5.4; N, 3.85. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₉NO₅S; C, 56.96; H, 5.63; N, 4.15%).

N-(7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-coumarinyl)valine (IV): M.p. 230-32° d; ν_{\max} (nujol): 3400 (broad), 3150 (broad), 1720, 1610 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 62.63; H, 6.27; N, 5.313. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₉O₅N; C, 62.95; H, 6.22; N, 4.59%).

N-(7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-coumarinyl)serine (V): M.p. 230° d; ν_{\max} (nujol): 3500 (broad), 3200 (broad), 1710, 1615 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 54.47; H, 5.5; N, 4.294. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₅O₆N.H₂O; C, 54.00; H, 5.46; N, 4.5%).

N-(7-Hydroxy-8-coumarinyl)glycine (VI): M.p. 275-76° d; ν_{\max} (nujol): 3400 (broad), 1720, 1600 cm^{-1} ; pmr (δ , CF₃COOH): 4.4 (2H, s, -NHCH₂-COOH), 4.95 (2H, s, -CH₂NH), 6.6 (1H, d, J=9Hz, H-3), 7.2 (1H, d, J=9Hz, H-6), 7.8 (1H, d, J=9Hz, H-5), 8.22 (1H, d, J=9Hz, H-4). (Found: C, 57.72; H, 4.52; N, 5.59. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₁O₅N; C, 57.83; H, 4.41; N, 5.62%).

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